
SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL FOR

**NEUROANATOMY OF THE MEKOSUCHINE
CROCODYLIAN *TRILOPHOSUCHUS RACKHAMI*
WILLIS, 1993**

**SUPPLEMENTAL DOCUMENT S2: MEASURING INSTRUCTIONS AND
SOURCES USED FOR THE COMPARATIVE NEUROANATOMY**

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This supplementary document to the study titled “Neuroanatomy of the mekosuchine crocodylian *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993” contains information on the measuring parameters for the crocodylomorph brain endocasts and endosseous labyrinths presented in Supplemental Document S4 (in .xlsx format). The measuring parameters and their abbreviations are listed in **Tables S2.1** and **S2.2** below. Additionally, instructions on how these measurements were obtained (both in Table 1 of the main text and in Supplemental Document S4) are illustrated in some of the figures included in this document.

For most specimens, the measurements were obtained either from data in the published literature or taken in ImageJ (<https://imagej.nih.gov/ij>) based on published figures or, where available, from interactive 3D PDF documents by using the Measuring Tool in Adobe Acrobat Pro DC version 21.0 (<https://www.adobe.com/au/acrobat/acrobat-pro.html>). The endosseous labyrinths of some taxa were measured in MeshLab 2020.12 (Cignoni *et al.*, 2008) by using the Measuring Tool. Several taxa were measured in Materialise Mimics 22.0 (Materialise NV, Belgium) using the Distance and Angle tools from the MEASURE menu. The sources for each taxon are given in **Table S2.3**.

Listed in **Table S2.1** are the measuring parameters and their abbreviations used in Supplemental Document S4. Out of the 22 listed parameters, 15 are originally from Pierce *et al.* (2017), while seven are introduced here for the first time (see **Tables 1** and **S2.1**). Three additional new parameters, measuring the angles of the semicircular canals, are measured only for *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993 and given in Table 1. Explanations on how to obtain the measurements for these parameters are provided in **Fig. S2.1** (see also figure 2 in Pierce *et al.*, 2017).

In addition to the brain endocast and endosseous labyrinth measurements, the morphometric data on a brain from a *Crocodylus porosus* Schneider, 1801 specimen (OUVC

10899) is also provided in Supplemental Document S4. The raw μ CT data for specimen OUVC 10899 was downloaded from MorphoSource, courtesy of Lawrence Witmer. The brain and brain endocast of OUVC 10899 (**Figs. S2.2–S2.5**) were digitally segmented in Materialise Mimics 22.0 at the University of Queensland. The measuring parameters for the brain and instructions on how they were measured are provided in **Table S2.2** and **Fig. S2.5**. The link to the raw μ CT data for OUVC 10899 is https://www.morphosource.org/biological_specimens/000S22084.

Table S2.1 List of parameters and their abbreviations used in measuring the brain endocasts and endosseous labyrinths. Unless indicated as **NEW**, the measuring parameters are based on those from Pierce *et al.* (2017).

Parameter	Abbreviation
Skull width between postorbitals, at the level of cerebral hemispheres	SW
Cephalic flexure angle	CFX
Pontine flexure angle	PFX
Brain endocast, length	eBL
Olfactory apparatus (endocast), length	eOAL
NEW Olfactory bulbs (endocast), width	eOBW
Brain endocast at cerebral hemispheres, width	eCRW
NEW Brain endocast at cerebral hemispheres, height	eCRH
NEW Midbrain region on brain endocast, width	eMBW
NEW Hindbrain region on brain endocast, height	eHBH
NEW Hindbrain region on brain endocast, width	eHBW
Hypophyseal fossa, width	eHFW
Hypophyseal fossa, height	eHFH
Hypophyseal fossa, length	eHFL
Endosseous labyrinth, height	ELH
Endosseous labyrinth, anteroposterior length	ELL
NEW Vestibular apparatus, height	VEH
NEW Common crus, height	CCRH
Endosseous cochlear duct, height	ECH
Anterior semicircular canal area	AA
Posterior semicircular canal area	PA
Lateral semicircular canal area	LA

Figure S2.1 Instructions for measuring the brain endocast and endosseous labyrinth as shown on the holotype specimen (QMF16856) of *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993. (A) Digital model of the cranium in dorsal view. (B–E) Brain endocast in: (B and D) left lateral, (C) dorsal, and (E) ventral views. (F–J) Right endosseous labyrinth in: (F and I) lateral, and (G, H and J) dorsal views. Cranium, brain endocast and endosseous labyrinth not to scale. For a high-resolution version of this figure, see the PDF file of **Figure S2.1** provided as a supplementary file. Abbreviations are explained in Table S2.1, except for: **AL**, angle between anterior and lateral semicircular canals; **AP**, angle between anterior and posterior semicircular canals; **PL**, angle between posterior and lateral semicircular canals.

Figure S2.2 Digital model of a head of a juvenile *Crocodylus porosus* Schneider, 1801. The head is made transparent in order to show the brain. (A) Dorsal, (B) ventral, and (C) right lateral views. Based on a personal digital reconstruction of specimen OUV 10899. Raw μ CT data available at MorphoSource (see link above), courtesy of Lawrence Witmer. For a high-resolution version of this figure, see the PDF file of **Figure S2.2** provided as a supplementary file.

Figure S2.3 Brain endocast with brain of a juvenile *Crocodylus porosus* Schneider, 1801. The brain endocast is made transparent in order to show the brain enclosed within. (A) Dorsal, (B) ventral, (C) right lateral, and (D) left lateral views. Based on a personal digital reconstruction of specimen OUVC 10899. Raw μ CT data available at MorphoSource (see link above), courtesy of Lawrence Witmer. For a high-resolution version of this figure, see the PDF file of **Figure S2.3** provided as a supplementary file.

Figure S2.4 Brain of a juvenile *Crocodylus porosus* Schneider, 1801. Brain in dorsal view, (A) non-annotated, and (B) annotated digital model. Brain in ventral view, (C) non-annotated, and (D) annotated digital model. Brain in right lateral view, (E) non-annotated, and (F) annotated digital model. Based on a personal digital reconstruction of specimen OUV 10899. Raw μ CT data available at MorphoSource (see link above), courtesy of Lawrence Witmer. For a high-resolution version of this figure, see the PDF file of **Figure S2.4** provided as a supplementary file. Abbreviations: **aur**, cerebellar auricle; **cbl**, cerebellum; **cer**, cerebral hemisphere; **die**, diencephalon; **inf**, infundibulum; **mdo**, medulla oblongata; **ob**, olfactory bulb; **opc**, optic chiasma; **opl**, optic lobe; **ot**, olfactory tract; **pns**, pons; **pty**, pituitary.

Table S2.2 List of parameters and their abbreviations used in measuring the brain of *Crocodylus porosus* Schneider, 1801, OUV 10899. The parameters are newly introduced here, although some are based on those proposed by Pierce *et al.* (2017).

Parameter	Abbreviation
Cephalic flexure angle	CFX
Pontine flexure angle	PFX
Brain, length	BL
Olfactory apparatus, length	OAL
Olfactory bulbs, width	OBW
Cerebral hemispheres, width	CRW
Cerebral hemispheres, height	CRH
Optic lobes, width	OPLW
Hindbrain, height	HBH
Cerebellum, width	CBW
Medulla, width	MDW
Pituitary, width	PW
Pituitary, height	PH
Pituitary, length	PL

Figure S2.5 Instructions for measuring the brain as shown on a specimen of a juvenile *Crocodylus porosus* Schneider, 1801. (A) Digital model of the head in dorsal view. (B–E) Brain in: (B and D) left lateral, (C) dorsal, and (E) ventral views. Head and brain not to scale. Based on a personal digital reconstruction of specimen OUV 10899. Raw μ CT data available at MorphoSource (see link above), courtesy of Lawrence Witmer. Abbreviations explained in Tables S2.1 and S2.2. For a high-resolution version of this figure, see the PDF file of **Figure S2.5** provided as a supplementary file.

Table S2.3 Sources, both from the literature and digitally examined specimens, used for comparative neuroanatomy and/or measurements. Specimen numbers that are underlined indicate that their endocranial elements have been examined based on a personal digital reconstruction.

Taxon	Sources for comparative neuroanatomy and/or measurements
<i>Aegisuchus witmeri</i>	Holliday & Gardner (2012)
<i>Agaresuchus fontisensis</i>	Serrano-Martínez <i>et al.</i> (2021)
<i>Agaresuchus subjuniperus</i>	Puértolas-Pascual <i>et al.</i> (2022)
<i>Alligator mississippiensis</i>	OUV 9761 (data related to Schwab <i>et al.</i> , 2020); USNM211232 (data related to Schwab <i>et al.</i> , 2020); USNM211233 (data related to Schwab <i>et al.</i> , 2020); Witmer & Ridgely (2008); Sereno & Larsson (2009); George & Holliday (2013); Dufeu & Witmer (2015); Serrano-Martínez (2018); Hu <i>et al.</i> (2021); Kuzmin <i>et al.</i> (2021)
<i>Allodaposuchus hulki</i>	Blanco <i>et al.</i> (2015)
<i>Almadasuchus figarii</i>	Leardi <i>et al.</i> (2020)
<i>Anatosuchus minor</i>	Sereno & Larsson (2009)
<i>Araripesuchus wegeneri</i>	Sereno & Larsson (2009)
<i>Arenysuchus gascabadiolorum</i>	Puértolas-Pascual <i>et al.</i> (2022)
<i>Baurusuchus</i> sp.	Dumont Jr <i>et al.</i> (2020)
<i>Caiman crocodilus</i>	FMNH 73711 (data related to Schwab <i>et al.</i> , 2020); Serrano-Martínez (2018)
<i>Caiman gasparinae</i>	Bona & Paulina Carabajal (2013)
<i>Campinasuchus dinizi</i>	Fonseca <i>et al.</i> (2020)
<i>Cricosaurus araucanensis</i>	Herrera (2015); Herrera <i>et al.</i> (2018)
<i>Cricosaurus schroederi</i>	MMGLV # (data related to Schwab <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
<i>Crocodylus acutus</i>	FMNH 59071 (data related to Schwab <i>et al.</i> , 2020); Colbert (1946)
<i>Crocodylus johnstoni</i>	Witmer <i>et al.</i> (2008)
<i>Crocodylus moreletii</i>	TMM M-4980 (data related to Schwab <i>et al.</i> , 2020); Franzosa (2004); Serrano-Martínez (2018)
<i>Crocodylus niloticus</i>	George & Holliday (2013); Serrano-Martínez (2018)
<i>Crocodylus porosus</i>	<u>OUV 10899</u> ; <u>QMJ48127</u> ; <u>QMJ52809</u>
<i>Crocodylus rhombifer</i>	<u>NMB AB50.0171</u>
<i>Crocodylus siamensis</i>	Kawabe <i>et al.</i> (2009)
<i>Diplocynodon tormis</i>	Serrano-Martínez <i>et al.</i> (2019a)
<i>Eopneumatosuchus colberti</i>	MNA V2460 (data related to Schwab <i>et al.</i> , 2020); Melstrom <i>et al.</i> (2021)
<i>Gavialis gangeticus</i>	TMM M-5490 (data related to Schwab <i>et al.</i> , 2020); ZIN 7249 (digital model courtesy of Ivan T. Kuzmin); Bona <i>et al.</i> (2017); Pierce <i>et al.</i> (2017); Serrano-Martínez (2018); Kuzmin <i>et al.</i> (2021)
' <i>Goniopholis pugnax</i> '	Edinger (1938)

Table S2.3 (continued)

Taxon	Sources for comparative neuroanatomy and/or measurements
<i>Gryposuchus neogaeus</i>	Bona <i>et al.</i> (2017)
<i>Gunggamarandu maunala</i>	<u>QMF548</u> (=QMF14.548, old registry number); Ristevski <i>et al.</i> (2021)
cf. <i>Hamadasuchus</i> sp.	ROM 54511 (digital model courtesy of David L. Dufeau); Dufeau (2011); George & Holliday (2013)
<i>Junggarsuchus sloani</i>	IVPP V14010 (data related to Schwab <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
<i>Leidyosuchus</i> sp.	Walsh & Knoll (2011)
<i>Leidyosuchus canadensis</i>	George & Holliday (2013)
<i>Lohuecosuchus megadontos</i>	Serrano-Martínez <i>et al.</i> (2019b)
<i>Macrospodylus bollensis</i>	Herrera <i>et al.</i> (2018); Wilberg <i>et al.</i> (2021)
<i>Mecistops cataphractus</i>	<u>TMM M-3529</u> ; Kuzmin <i>et al.</i> (2021)
<i>Melanosuchus niger</i>	George & Holliday (2013); Serrano-Martínez (2018); Fonseca <i>et al.</i> (2020)
' <i>Metriorhynchus</i> ' cf. ' <i>M.</i> ' <i>brachyrhynchus</i>	Schwab <i>et al.</i> (2021)
' <i>Metriorhynchus</i> ' cf. ' <i>M.</i> ' <i>westermanni</i>	Fernández <i>et al.</i> (2011)
<i>Mourasuchus arendsi</i>	Bona <i>et al.</i> (2013)
<i>Osteolaemus tetraspis</i>	<u>FMNH 98936</u> ; Serrano-Martínez (2018); Kuzmin <i>et al.</i> (2021)
<i>Paleosuchus palpebrosus</i>	FMNH 69869 (digital model courtesy of David L. Dufeau); Dufeau (2011)
<i>Paludirex vincenti</i>	<u>"Geoff Vincent's specimen"</u> ; Ristevski <i>et al.</i> (2020a, b)
<i>Pelagosaurus typus</i>	Pierce <i>et al.</i> (2017)
<i>Pholidosaurus meyeri</i>	Edinger (1938); Hopson, (1979)
<i>Pholidosaurus schauburgensis</i>	Edinger (1938)
<i>Plagiophthalmosuchus</i> cf. <i>P.</i> <i>gracilirostris</i>	Brusatte <i>et al.</i> (2016)
<i>Protosuchus haughtoni</i>	BP 1 4770 (data related to Schwab <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
<i>Rhabdognathus aslerensis</i>	Erb & Turner (2021)
<i>Rukwasuchus yajabaliyekundu</i>	Sertich & O'Connor (2014)
<i>Sebecus icaeorhinus</i>	Colbert (1946); Hopson (1979)
<i>Simosuchus clarki</i>	Kley <i>et al.</i> (2010)
<i>Thalattosuchus superciliosus</i>	MNHN.F RJN 256 (data related to Schwab <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
<i>Tomistoma schlegelii</i>	<u>TMM M-6342</u> ; USNM21 1322 (data related to Schwab <i>et al.</i> , 2020); Kuzmin <i>et al.</i> (2021)
<i>Torvoneustes coryphaeus</i>	MJML K1863 (data related to Schwab <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
<i>Uberabasuchus terrificus</i>	Fonseca <i>et al.</i> (2020)
Undescribed "sphenosuchian"	NCSM 21722 (data related to Schwab <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
<i>Zulmasuchus querejazus</i>	Pochat-Cottilloux <i>et al.</i> (2021)

Taxonomic remarks

- According to Salisbury *et al.* (1999) '*Goniopholis pugnax*' Koken, 1887 is a nomen dubium.
- The comparative material of the taxon herein referred as cf. *Hamadasuchus* sp. belongs to specimens that were assigned to *Hamadasuchus rebouli* Buffetaut, 1994 by Larsson & Sues (2007). However, more recent studies (Cavin *et al.*, 2010; Ibrahim *et al.*, 2020; Nicholl *et al.*, 2021) expressed doubt on whether those specimens can be referred to *H. rebouli*. Hence, I provisionally refer to that material as cf. *Hamadasuchus* sp. until a reassessment is published.
- The endocranial morphology of *Mourasuchus arendsi* Bocquentin Villanueva, 1984 was described by Bona *et al.* (2013) as *Mourasuchus nativus* (Gasparini, 1985). Herein I follow the more recent revision by Scheyer & Delfino (2016) who regard *M. nativus* as a junior synonym of *M. arendsi*.
- '*Steneosaurus*' *bollensis* von Jäger, 1828 was recently revised into *Macrospondylus bollensis* by Johnson *et al.* (2020). This concerns specimen BSPG 1984 I258, which was formerly referred to as *Steneosaurus bollensis* by Herrera *et al.* (2018).
- '*Steneosaurus*' *gracilirostris* Westphal, 1961 was recently revised into *Plagiophthalmosuchus gracilirostris* by Johnson *et al.* (2020). This concerns specimen NHMUK PV OR 33095, which was formerly referred to as *Steneosaurus* cf. *gracilirostris* by Brusatte *et al.* (2016).

INSTITUTIONAL ABBREVIATIONS

BP, Bernard Price Institute, Johannesburg, South Africa (now the Evolutionary Studies Institute at the University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg, South Africa)

BSPG, Bayerische Staatssammlung für Paläontologie und Geologie, Munich, Germany

FMNH, Field Museum of Natural History, Chicago, Illinois, U. S. A.

IVPP, Institute of Vertebrate Paleontology and Paleoanthropology, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing, China

MJML, Museum of Jurassic Marine Life, Kimmeridge, Dorset, England, United Kingdom

MMGLV, Mindener Museum für Geschichte, Landes- und Volkskunde, Minden, Germany

MNA, Museum of Northern Arizona, Flagstaff, Arizona, U. S. A.

MNHN, Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris, France (F, fossil)

NCSM, North Carolina State Museum, Raleigh, North Carolina, U. S. A.

NHMUK, Natural History Museum, London, England, United Kingdom (OR, old register; PV, vertebrate palaeontology collection)

NMB, National Museum of the Bahamas, Nassau, Commonwealth of the Bahamas

OUVC, Ohio University Vertebrate Collections, Athens, Ohio, U.S.A.

QM, Queensland Museum, Brisbane, Queensland, Australia (F, fossil)

ROM, Royal Ontario Museum, Toronto, Canada

TMM, Texas Memorial Museum, Austin, Texas, U. S. A.

USNM, National Museum of Natural History, Washington, D. C., U. S. A.

ZIN, Zoological Institute, Russian Academy of Sciences, Saint Petersburg, Russia

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